

Corn cob ethanol extract (*Zea mays* L.) treatment on malondialdehyde, C-reactive protein, caspase-3, polymorphonuclear cells, pancreatic β -cell necrosis, and blood sugar in Wistar rats with diabetes mellitus

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the anti-diabetic activity of corn cob extract through laboratory experiments, testing its effects on malondialdehyde (MDA), C-reactive protein (CRP), caspase-3, polymorphonuclear (PMN), pancreatic beta cell necrosis, and blood sugar in Wistar mice with diabetes mellitus (DM). The anti-diabetic activity of corn cobs was compared with metformin and a combination of both, using 35 male Wistar rats (8 weeks old). The rats were divided into five groups: KN (normal), K- (DM), K+ (metformin therapy 45 mg/kgBW), P1 (corn cob extract therapy 520 mg/kgBW), and P2 (metformin therapy 45 mg/kgBW + corn cob extract). DM was induced by administering nicotinamide 100 mg/kgBW followed by streptozotocin 65 mg/kgBW. After 21 days of intervention, significant differences were observed in MDA and blood sugar levels ($p < 0.05$), as well as in caspase-3, polymorphonuclear, and pancreatic beta cell necrosis ($p < 0.05$). In conclusion, corn cob extract (*Zea mays* L.) provides a strong anti-diabetic effect, and its combination with melatonin shows a synergistic effect that can be utilized in DM therapy.

Keywords

corn cob, diabetes mellitus, metformin

Introduction

In the modern world, the number of people with diabetes mellitus (DM) is increasing, which is considered a new

pandemic. Diabetes is a cause of premature death from chronic diseases (Wronka et al. 2022). Insulin resistance in diabetics results in disruption of redox balance, increasing the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS)

and reducing antioxidant defenses (ADA 2020). Excessive lipid modification due to hyperglycemia and insulin resistance increases malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, which correlate with inflammation in pancreatic β -cell tissue (Fitriana et al. 2017). Pancreatic β -cell damage due to inflammation determines polymorphonuclear (PMN) levels (Manosudprasit et al. 2017). Inflammation caused by pancreatic β -cell disorders in diabetics increases C-reactive protein (CRP) levels. Chronic hyperglycemia can trigger caspase-3 expression and apoptosis; increased caspase-3 expression and apoptosis worsen the condition of diabetic patients (Hua et al. 2020).

Metformin is a first-line biguanide drug commonly used in type 2 DM patients (Buđak et al. 2016; Thomas and Gregg 2017). Its mechanism for reducing blood sugar levels involves increasing glucose utilization in tissues, which is influenced by the activity of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) (Banjarnahor and Wangko 2013). The limited effects of metformin therapy include bloating (58.4%) and other gastrointestinal symptoms (41.6%) (Riwu et al. 2015), as well as nausea, edema, fluid retention, weight gain, and risk of heart failure (Yang et al. 2020). The utilization of natural antioxidants is an alternative therapy in diabetes, functioning by inhibiting free radicals and preventing diabetic complications (Prawitasari 2019). Based on pharmacological phytochemical research, corn cobs contain natural antioxidants that can counteract free radicals. Ethanol extract of corn cobs (*Zea mays* L.) contains flavonoids and polyphenols (Saleh et al. 2012). Flavonoids can directly bind to free radicals by donating hydrogen atoms or by single electron transfer. As intracellular antioxidants, flavonoids work through inhibition of free radical-producing enzymes such as xanthine oxidase, lipoxygenase, protein kinase C, cyclooxygenase, microsomal monooxygenase, mitochondrial succinoxidase, and NADPH oxidase (Banjarnahor and Ar-tanti 2014). This study analyzed the effect of ethanol extract of corn cob (*Zea mays* L.) on malondialdehyde, C-reactive protein, caspase-3, polymorphonuclear, pancreatic β -cell necrosis, and blood sugar levels in a Wistar rat DM model. Thus, it is hoped that administering corn cob ethanol extract (*Zea mays* L.) can help stabilize blood sugar levels and reduce the risk of complications that may occur with long-term metformin consumption.

Materials and methods

Animal experiment

Forty male Wistar rats, aged 8 weeks and weighing 200–250 g, were used. Rats were acclimatized for 7 days at 22 ± 2 °C in polycarbonate cages, with 3–4 rats per cage. The experimental protocol was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee of Dr. Moewardi General Hospital (No. 1.612/XII/HREC/2022). Research activities were conducted at the Integrated Research and Testing Laboratory, Gajah Mada University.

Making diabetes model mice

Male Wistar rats were induced to develop a diabetes model using nicotinamide (NA) at 100 mg/kg body weight (BW), followed 15 minutes later by a single dose of streptozotocin (STZ) at 65 mg/kgBW. Streptozotocin was dissolved in 0.01 M citrate buffer (pH 4.5) and used within 10–15 minutes of preparation.

Grouping of research animals

Based on the sample size determined by WHO in 1993, each group should contain at least five rats (Kurniati and Rohmani 2017). Three rats were added per group to account for potential exclusions. Animals were randomly divided into five groups:

- Normal group (KN): Normal male Wistar rats without DM; no intervention; given standard feed.
- **Negative control group (K-)**: Male Wistar rats with DM; no intervention; given standard feed.
- Positive control group (K+): Male Wistar rats with DM treated with metformin at 45 mg/kgBW in 2–3 cc per administration.
- **Treatment group 1 (P1)**: DM model rats treated with 60% ethanol extract of corn cob (*Zea mays* L.) at 520 mg/kgBW in 2–3 cc per administration.
- **Treatment group 2 (P2)**: DM model rats treated with metformin (45 mg/kgBW) and ethanol extract of corn cob (*Zea mays* L.) at 520 mg/kgBW in 2–3 cc per administration.

In each group, one rat was excluded due to abnormal blood sugar levels (>200 mg/dL in the non-diabetic group or <200 mg/dL in the diabetic group), signs of weakness, illness, or death. Each group ultimately consisted of seven rats.

Dosing protocol of corn cob ethanol extract and standard therapy:

- Corn cob ethanol extract
Previous studies identified that a dose of 520 mg/kgBW of corn cob ethanol extract effectively lowered blood sugar levels.
- Metformin

The usual dose of metformin HCl for humans = 500 mg
Conversion of 200 g Wistar rats = $500 \text{ mg} \times 0.018^{21}$
= 9 mg/200 mg rat

Dose of 200–250 g weight Wistar rats

$$= \frac{200 \text{ mg} - 250 \text{ mg}}{200} \times 9 \text{ g}$$

$$= \frac{1800 \text{ mg} - 2250 \text{ mg}}{200}$$

$$= 9 \text{ mg} - 11.25 \text{ mg}$$

Dose of 1 Kg weight Wistar rats = $\frac{1000 \text{ mg}}{200} \times 9 \text{ mg}$
= 45 mg/KgBW tikus

Blood sampling

Non-heparinized tubes were used to collect blood samples for blood sugar levels before and after the intervention. Heparinized capillary tubes were used to collect blood samples from the retro-orbital area for malondialdehyde and C-reactive protein examinations, both before and after the intervention. Blood samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes.

Examination procedure

Blood sugar level was examined by spectrophotometer, malondialdehyde by ELISA kit, and C-reactive protein by ELISA kit; all were tested twice. Examination of polymorphonuclear expression and pancreatic β -cell necrosis was performed using hematoxylin–eosin staining, and caspase-3 was assessed by immunohistochemistry.

Spectrophotometer examination was performed by collecting blood through the rat's orbital sinus using a 1 mL microhematocrit tube. The sample was then centrifuged for 10 minutes at 2500 rpm. The obtained serum (10 μ L) was mixed with 1 mL of GOD-POD reagent, vortexed for 5 seconds, and incubated for 10 minutes at 37 °C. The absorbance of the sample was measured using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 500 nm. For ELISA examination, 50 μ L of each standard solution and 40 μ L of blood plasma sample were added to the designated wells. In the wells containing the samples, 10 μ L of anti-sample solution was added, followed by 50 μ L of Streptavidin-HRP in both the standard and sample wells. The microplate was then sealed and incubated for 60 minutes at 37 °C. After incubation, the microplate was unsealed and washed with 300 μ L of wash buffer solution for 30–60 seconds. The washing step was repeated five times, and the plate was allowed to dry. After drying, 50 μ L each of Substrate A and Substrate B solutions were added to each well. The microplate was incubated again for 10 minutes at 37 °C in the dark. After incubation, 50 μ L of stop solution was added to each well. Absorbance was then measured at a wavelength of 450 nm using a microplate reader.

The results of the examination were compared with the control group, namely male Wistar rats that were not diabetic and did not receive intervention, and male Wistar rats with diabetes that were not given any intervention. In addition, the results were also compared with other groups that received different interventions.

Statistical analysis

The data were coded and entered using SPSS Statistics version 24. ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis statistical tests were used to identify differences in each group. ANOVA was used when the data were normally distributed and met homogeneity requirements. The next step to determine the most significant differences within the

group was a post hoc test using LSD (least significant difference). The Kruskal–Wallis test was used when the data were not normally distributed (based on the Shapiro–Wilk test) and not homogeneous, with a significance level of <0.05 . The next step to determine the most significant differences in the group was the Mann–Whitney U statistical test. Data are presented in tables and figures.

Result

Malondialdehyde

Based on the ANOVA statistical test, there was no difference in the mean value of malondialdehyde (MDA) levels among all groups before the intervention. However, a significant difference was observed after the intervention. The lowest mean value was found in the P2 treatment group (metformin 45 mg/kgBW + corncob ethanol extract 520 mg/kgBW) (Table 1, Fig. 1).

Table 1. Comparison of malondialdehyde level before and after intervention.

Groups	Before				After			
	MDA levels				MDA levels			
	(mean \pm SD)	Min	Max	<i>p</i> value	(mean \pm SD)	Min	Max	<i>p</i> value
KN	(1.18 \pm 0.8)	0.96	1.49	0.896	(1.19 \pm 0.27)	0.76	1.58	
K(-)	(1.28 \pm 0.39)	0.7	1.88		(1.41 \pm 0.20)	1.22	1.79	
K(+)	(1.28 \pm 0.16)	1.03	1.45		(1.21 \pm 0.13)	0.97	1.39	0.003
P1	(1.23 \pm 0.05)	1.15	1.3		(1.06 \pm 0.14)	0.82	1.3	
P2	(1.28 \pm 0.20)	0.93	1.49		(0.97 \pm 0.14)	0.73	1.21	

Values are presented as mean \pm SD. ANOVA statistical values with $p < 0.05$.

Figure 1. Changes in mean malondialdehyde levels before and after intervention in all groups. Values are presented as means. Post hoc statistics compare each group with the normal group (*) and the negative control group (#), with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

C-reactive protein

The results of the ANOVA statistical test showed that there was no significant difference in the mean C-reactive protein levels in all groups before and after the intervention. However, clinically, the greatest decrease was observed in the P2 group. A significant difference in CRP levels was found between the negative control group and the P2 group (Table 2, Fig. 2).

Table 2. Comparison of C-reactive protein levels before and after intervention.

Groups	Before				After			
	(mean ± SD)	Min	Max	p value	(mean ± SD)	Min	Max	p value
KN	(2.52 ± 0.27)	2.26	2.95	0.796	(2.53 ± 0.18)	2.27	2.75	
K(-)	(2.64 ± 0.32)	2.20	3.11		(2.72 ± 0.32)	2.32	3.06	
K(+)	(2.66 ± 0.12)	2.46	2.79		(2.43 ± 0.29)	2.09	2.90	0.079
P1	(2.75 ± 0.25)	2.38	3.06		(2.56 ± 0.25)	2.23	2.97	
P2	(2.67 ± 0.50)	2.10	3.61		(2.27 ± 0.29)	1.88	2.60	

Values are presented as mean ± SD and ANOVA statistical values with $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Changes in mean C-reactive protein levels before and after intervention in all groups. Values are presented as mean and post hoc statistics of each group compared with the normal group (*), with negative control (#) compared statistically ($p < 0.05$).

Polymorphonuclear

There was no sign of inflammation in pancreatic β -cells in the KN group, but inflammation was observed in all diabetic male Wistar rat groups. After the intervention, the P2 group showed the lowest expression of inflammation compared to the positive control and P1 groups (Table 3, Figs 3, 4).

Table 3. Polymorphonuclear after intervention in all groups.

Groups	Polymorphonuclear			Kruskal-Wallis p value
	(mean ± SD)	Min	Max	
KN	(0 ± 0)	0	0	< 0.001
K (-)	(17.1 ± 69.8)	10	25	
K (+)	(7.14 ± 26.7)	5	10	
P1	(6.42 ± 24.3)	5	10	
P2	(2.85 ± 26.7)	0	5	

Values are presented as mean ± SD and Kruskal-Wallis statistical values with $p < 0.05$.

Figure 4. Polymorphonuclear histopathology 200× after intervention in all groups. Values are presented with a black arrow.

Caspase-3

The Kruskal-Wallis statistical test showed a significant difference in caspase-3 immunohistochemistry results among all groups after the intervention. The combination therapy of metformin and corn cob ethanol extract showed the most favorable outcome. A statistical difference was found between the K(-) group and others, while there was no significant difference between the KN group and the P2 group (Table 4, Fig. 5).

Table 4. Caspase-3 levels after intervention in all groups.

Groups	Caspase-3			Kruskal-Wallis p value
	(mean ± SD)	Min	Max	
KN	(10 ± 2.88)	5	15	< 0.001
K (-)	(58.5 ± 19.5)	30	80	
K (+)	(16.4 ± 8.01)	5	25	
P1	(26.4 ± 4.75)	20	30	
P2	(12.8 ± 6.96)	0	25	

Values are presented as mean ± SD and Kruskal-Wallis statistical values with $p < 0.05$.

Figure 5. Mean caspase-3 after intervention in all groups. Values are presented as mean and post hoc statistics of each group compared with the normal group (*), with negative control (#) compared statistically ($p < 0.05$).

Pancreatic β -cell necrosis

The Kruskal-Wallis statistical test showed differences in pancreatic β -cell necrosis among all groups. The mean necrosis level in the combination therapy group (P2) was close to the mean of the normal group, although the maximum value in the P2 group was higher than in the normal control. The normal control group did not show any expression of pancreatic β -cell necrosis, while histopathological examination of the P2 group showed the least expression among the diabetic groups (Table 5, Figs 6, 7).

Table 5. Pancreatic β -cell necrosis levels after intervention in all groups.

Group	Pancreatic beta cell necrosis (mean \pm SD)	Kruskal		Kruskal–Wallis p value
		Min Value	Max Value	
Normal Control	(0 \pm 0)	0	0	< 0.001
Negative Control	(37.8 \pm 12.8)	25	60	
Positive Control	(10.7 \pm 6.7)	5	20	
Treatment P1	(10 \pm 7.07)	5	20	
Treatment P2	(3.57 \pm 2.4)	0	5	

Values are presented as mean \pm SD and Kruskal–Wallis statistical values with $p < 0.05$.

Figure 6. Mean pancreatic β -cell necrosis after intervention in all groups. Values are presented as mean and post hoc statistics of each group compared with the normal group (*), with negative control (#) compared statistically ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 7. Histopathologic 200 \times picture showing necrosis in pancreatic β -cells (red arrow).

Blood sugar levels

The ANOVA test before and after the intervention showed significant differences in mean blood sugar levels in all

Table 6. Differences in blood sugar levels before and after intervention in all groups.

Groups	Before				After			
	(mean \pm SD)	Min	Max	p value	(mean \pm SD)	Min	Max	p value
KN	(154.4 \pm 23.93)	131.9	198.9	<0.001	(170.1 \pm 22.4)	149.4	190.8	
K(-)	(374.3 \pm 80.09)	219.5	458.9		(447.4 \pm 40.4)	410	484.8	
K(+)	(403.6 \pm 43.02)	356.6	451.0		(222.6 \pm 45.5)	180.5	264.6	<0.001
P1	(318.0 \pm 112.35)	214.4	495.9		(205.6 \pm 54.6)	155.03	256.19	
P2	(369.2 \pm 88.63)	210.8	446.3		(147.9 \pm 37.8)	122.9	182.9	

Values are presented as mean \pm SD and ANOVA statistical values with $p < 0.05$.

Figure 8. Mean difference in blood sugar levels before and after intervention in all groups. Values are presented as mean and post hoc statistics of each group compared with the normal group (*), with negative control (#) compared statistically ($p < 0.05$).

groups. The greatest reduction was observed in the combination group receiving metformin (45 mg/kgBW) and corncob ethanol extract (520 mg/kgBW). After the intervention, there was a significant difference between the K(-) group and the P2 group, while there was no significant difference between the KN and P2 groups.

Discussion

Streptozotocin generates highly reactive free radicals that damage cell membranes, proteins, and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), adversely affecting insulin production in the pancreatic β -cells of the islets of Langerhans (Saputra et al. 2018).

Statistical analysis before the intervention revealed no significant differences in malondialdehyde levels among all groups ($p = 0.896$). In preparation for the study, external factors such as cage capacity, room temperature, humidity, and diet were controlled to avoid stress in Wistar rats. However, internal stress conditions during the research process could not be controlled. Stress experienced by the male Wistar rats likely contributed to increased MDA levels, as acute stress activates the sympathetic nervous system, leading to the release of epinephrine and norepinephrine in a “fight or flight” response, which increases MDA levels (Spiers et al. 2015).

There was a significant difference in MDA levels after the intervention. In the positive control group, P1 treatment and P2 treatment decreased. The most decrease in the P2 treatment group was 0.208 nmol/gram. Effects of polyphenols in plants given as combination therapy or additional therapy can reduce insulin resistance by regulating carbohydrate metabolism and reducing free radical levels (Saleh et al. 2012). This condition causes the P2 group to decrease more than the other intervention groups because metformin works by reducing the gluconeogenesis process and utilizing energy sources derived from carbohydrates (Buldak et al. 2016).

Results of the ANOVA statistical test stated that there was no significant difference in C-reactive protein levels

before and after the intervention. Internal stress conditions that could not be controlled in this study caused an increase in CRP levels in the rats used in this study. Stress causes an increase in cortisol and adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH), which contributes to the increase in IL6 and CRP (Shamoon et al. 2021). C-reactive protein is an early marker of infection or inflammation, with the highest level at 2 hours after exposure and a maximum after 48 hours, and will decrease periodically (Chandra and Fatoni 2021).

Patients with DM who experience complications and without complications will show an increase in polymorphonuclear levels (Manosudprasit et al. 2017). The mechanism involves increasing intracellular enzymes that counteract oxidative stress. Treatment with antioxidants increases nitric oxide (NO), thereby repairing endothelial and mitochondrial cells, which results in a decrease in nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate oxidase (NADPH) oxidase of cells.

The results of this study are in accordance with the results of the study that by giving antioxidants in the form of anthocyanins from purple sweet potatoes, caspase-3 levels in DM model rats (Prakosa et al. 2017). The activity of antioxidants protects endothelial cells from metabolic damage that results in oxidative stress. Antioxidants inhibit the occurrence of apoptosis through a protective system on the membrane of mitochondria and a decrease in cell response to caspase-3.

Pancreatic β -cell damage after being given intervention for 21 days, data were obtained that in the intervention group the average pancreatic β -cell necrosis in all treatment groups and in the positive control group showed the expression of β -cell necrosis, and pancreatic β -cell necrosis was higher than in the P1 group. In the P2 treatment group, the average pancreatic β -cell necrosis was the lowest at 3.571, with the lowest value of 0 and the highest value of 5. The results of this study are similar to the results of previous studies, namely the DM model rat group given soursop leaf extract and moringa leaves containing polyphenols, which experienced improvement in pancreatic β -cell damage (Pratama et al. 2020; Anggi et al. 2020).

Antioxidant administration has the potential to repair the structure of pancreatic beta cells. Metformin given to male Wistar rats has the potential to help reduce hyperglycemia so that it helps reduce free radicals, so that the administration of metformin and the administration of corn cob ethanol extract have more potential to reduce pancreatic β -cell necrosis.

Male Wistar rats induced with streptozotocin and nicotinamide experienced elevated blood sugar levels (>200 mg/dL), which decreased after 21 days of intervention. The control group experienced the highest blood sugar increase (421.5 mg/dL). Streptozotocin and nicotinamide are diabetogenic agents that induce hyperglycemia (Fitriana et al. 2017; Anggi et al. 2020).

In the intervention groups – namely, the positive control, P1, and P2 – blood sugar levels decreased, with the

greatest reduction seen in the P2 group, which received metformin and corn cob ethanol extract for 21 days.

Metformin is an oral antidiabetic drug that has been used for many years. Its mechanism involves reducing gluconeogenesis, thereby enhancing glucose utilization in the body (Furdiyanti et al. 2017). Antioxidants also contribute to improving hyperglycemia in diabetic patients (Prawitasari 2019). In DM model Wistar rats, papaya leaf extract (*Carica papaya*) containing antioxidants at doses of 250 mg/kgBW and 500 mg/kgBW reduced blood sugar levels within 12 hours (Senduk et al. 2016).

Most plants and fruits contain polyphenols, which are antioxidants capable of neutralizing free radicals and reducing reactive oxygen species. The accumulation of blood sugar due to altered fat metabolism leads to free radical formation. An intervention combining metformin and polyphenols from corn cob ethanol extract has a greater effect on normalizing blood sugar levels.

Conclusion

Corn cob ethanol extract intervention showed improvements in malondialdehyde, C-reactive protein, caspase-3, polymorphonuclear, pancreatic beta cell necrosis, and blood sugar levels. Coadministration with metformin showed better results on blood and Langerhans islet cells.

The greatest decrease in malondialdehyde levels was observed in group P2, where the level before intervention was 1.29 and after intervention was 0.97 (a decrease of 0.32). The decrease in group P2 was greater than in group K(+) (0.07) and group P1 (0.18). The reduction in blood sugar after 21 days of intervention in group P2 was 220.8. These data show that the P2 group experienced the greatest reduction, compared to K+ (112.4) and P1 (181).

Therefore, it can be concluded that the combination of metformin and corn cob ethanol extract has a better impact on improving the condition of diabetes mellitus patients, especially with respect to malondialdehyde, blood sugar, C-reactive protein, caspase-3, polymorphonuclear, and pancreatic beta cell necrosis levels.

Considering that the results of this study showed that ethanol extract of corn cobs combined with standard drugs produced better outcomes than standard drugs alone, further research should be conducted using a combination of ethanol extract of corn cobs and standard therapy in female mice, given that diabetes mellitus affects both sexes.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

Clinical trials: Health Research Ethics Committee Dr. Moewardi General Hospital Number. 1.612/XII/HREC/2022.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Health Research Ethics Committee Dr. Moewardi General Hospital Number. 1.612/XII/HREC/2022.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

References

- American Diabetes Association (2020) Classification and Diagnosis of Diabetes: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2020 Diabetes Care 43: S14–31. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc20-S002>
- Anggi V, Tandji J, Veronika V (2020) Total flavonoid dan efektivitas ekstrak etanol biji kelor (*Moringa oleifera* L.) asal kota palu sulawesi tengah terhadap histopatologi pankreas tikus putih jantan (*Rattus norvegicus*) yang diinduksi streptozotocin. Jurnal Ilmiah Manuntung 6(1): 24–31. <https://doi.org/10.51352/jim.v6i1.294>
- Banjarnahor E, Wangko S (2013) Sel beta pankreas sintesis dan sekresi insulin. Jurnal Biomedik (Jbm) 4(3). <https://doi.org/10.35790/jbm.4.3.2012.795>
- Banjarnahor S, Artanti N (2014) Antioxidant properties of flavonoids. Medical Journal of Indonesia 23(4): 239–244. <https://doi.org/10.13181/mji.v23i4.1015>
- Buldak Ł, Łabuzek K, Buldak RJ, Machnik G, Boldys A, Basiak M, Bogusław O (2016) Metformin reduces the expression of NADPH oxidase and increases the expression of antioxidative enzymes in human monocytes/macrophages cultured in vitro. Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine 11(3): 1095–1103. <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2016.2977>
- Chandra HK, Fatoni AZ (2021) Peranan C-Reactive Protein (CRP) pada pasien sepsis di Intensive Care Unit (ICU). Journal of Anaesthesia and Pain 2(1): 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jap.2021.002.01.01>
- Fitriana I, Wijayanti AD, Sari PW, Satria RGD, Setiawan DCB, Fibrianto YH, Nugroho WS (2017) Levels of malondialdehyde in Type 2 diabetes mellitus rats induced mesenchymal stem cell-conditioned. Media Acta Veterinaria Indonesiana. Fakultas Kedokteran Hewan IPB 5(1): 29–36. <https://doi.org/10.29244/avi.5.1.29-36>
- Furdiyanti NH, Luhurningyay FP, Yulianti RS (2017) Evaluasi dosis dan interaksi obat antidiabetika oral pada pasien diabetes mellitus tipe II. Jurnal Manajemen Dan Pelayanan Farmasi 7(4): 191–196.
- Hua L, Wang FQ, Du HW, Fan J, Wang YF, Wang LQ, Shi XW (2020) Up-regulation of caspase-3 by high glucose in chondrocyte involves the cytoskeleton aggregation. European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Sciences 24(11): 5925–5932. https://doi.org/10.26355/eurrev_202006_21485
- Kurniati ID, Rohmani A (2017) Kersen fruit extract (*Muntingia calabura*) decreases the number of goblet cells in rats exposed to cigarette smoked. Jurnal Kedokteran dan Kesehatan 13(2): 144. <https://doi.org/10.24853/jkk.13.2.144-152>
- Manosudprasit A, Kantarci A, Hasturk H, Stephens D, Van Dyke TE (2017) Spontaneous PMN apoptosis in type 2 diabetes and the impact of periodontitis. Journal of Leukocyte Biology 102(6): 1431–1440. <https://doi.org/10.1189/jlb.4A0416-209RR>
- Noushad S, Ahmed S, Ansari B, Mustafa U-H, Saleem Y, Hina H (2021) Physiological biomarkers of chronic stress: A systematic review. Introduction International Journal of Health Sciences 15(5): 46–59.
- Prakosa AG, Ratnawati R, Prabawati RK (2017) The effect of purple sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* L.) anthocyanin on the expression of caspase-3 in brain tissue of diabetes mellitus type 2- induced rats abstract. Majalah Kesehatan FKUB 4(2): 52–58. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.majalahkesehatan.2017.004.02.1>
- Pratama RY, Pranitasari N, Purwaningsari D (2020) Pengaruh ekstrak daun sirsak terhadap gambaran histopatologi pankreas rattus norvegicus jantan yang diinduksi aloksan. Hang Tuah Medical Journal 17: 116–129. <https://doi.org/10.30649/htmj.v17i2.159>
- Prawitasari DS (2019) Diabetes melitus dan antioksidan. Jurnal Kesehatan Dan Kedokteran 1(1): 48–52. <https://doi.org/10.24123/kesdok.V1i1.2496>
- Riwu M, Subarnas A, Lestari K (2015) The correlation of age factor, administration, and metformin dose against risk of side effect on type 2 diabetes mellitus. Indonesian Journal of Clinical Pharmacy 4(3): 151–61. <https://doi.org/10.15416/ijcp.2015.4.3.151>
- Saleh LP, Suryanto E, Yudistira A (2012) Aktivitas antioksidan dari ekstrak tongkol Jagung (*Zea mays* L.). Pharmacon 1(2): 20–24. <https://doi.org/10.35799/jm.1.1.2012.422>

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- Saputra NT, Suartha IN, Dharmayudha AAGO (2018) Diabetagonik agent streptozocin to make white rats male diabetes mellitus. *Buletin Veteriner Udayana* 10(2): e116. <https://doi.org/10.24843/bulvet.2018.v10.i02.p02>
- Senduk CCC, Awaloei H, Nangoy E (2016) Uji efek ekstrak daun papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) terhadap kadar gula darah tikus wistar (*Rattus norvegicus*) yang diinduksi aloksan. *Jurnal E-Biomedik* 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.35790/ebm.4.1.2016.12291>
- Spiers JG, Chen HJC, Sernia C, Lavidis NA (2015) Activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal stress axis induces cellular oxidative stress. *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 9(JAN): 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2014.00456>
- Thomas I, Gregg B (2017) Metformin; a review of its history and future: from lilac to longevity. *Pediatric Diabetes* 18(1): 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pedi.12473>
- Wronka M, Krzemińska J, Młynarska E, Rysz J, Franczyk B (2022) The influence of lifestyle and treatment on oxidative stress and inflammation in diabetes. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 23(24). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms232415743>
- Yang SC, Hsu CY, Chou WL, Fang JY, Chuang SY (2020) Bioactive agent discovery from the natural compounds for the treatment of type 2 diabetes rat model. *Molecules* 25(23). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25235713>